

Recommendation 18:

Using 'Mobile devices' to meet the societal need 'Faster and transparent access to PS services'

Actual solutions and services:

The growing number of mobile devices among the citizens and the use of e-government apps improves the access to governmental services. The number of mobile devices in the public sector itself will also lead to a growing usage of apps and thus to a further improvement of mobile governmental services.

Some examples are:

- ECIM Smart Mobility API
- Gov2go app (personal government assistant)
- Commercial Driver License (CDL) practice knowledge test mobile application
- Whim, Mobility-as-a-Service App, linking all transport networks in Finland and suggesting travel routes using all available means of transport

SWOT Analysis

Strengths

- **Ease of communication.**
- **Flexibility and dynamicity.**
- **Portability.**
- **Efficiency.**
- **Support for several applications – all-in-one device.**

Weaknesses

- Internet access required for certain functions.
- Variable connectivity.
- Hindering real human interaction.
- Increasing the probability of accidents.

Opportunities

- **Public Services reaching more people.**
- **Increased personalisation opportunities.**
- **Increased sensory data collection.**
- **Enablement of novel technologies related to mobile devices (wearables, biometrics, eIDs, etc.).**

Threats

- Cyberattacks and security breaches.
- Privacy and Personal Data.
- Vendor lock-in.

Faster and transparent access to public sector services:

The societal demand for a trustworthy public sector resonates until today. This need also includes issues such as better quality public services – fairness and customer service standards in public service provision . Informants mentioned establishing trust in governance, voicing their opinions, accessing timely and accurate information, unlinking public sector and politics as some of the key needs under this header. One informant expressed his opinion as: "A clear point of authority to be established (often have to roam offices because it is not clear the authority for a particular task)."

Mobile devices:

*A mobile device (or handheld computer) is a small computing device, typically small enough to hold and operate in the hand and having an operating system, capable of running mobile apps. These may provide a diverse range of functions. Typically, the device will have a display screen with a small numeric or alphanumeric keyboard or a touchscreen providing a virtual keyboard and buttons (icons) on screen. Many mobile devices can connect to the internet and interconnect with other devices via Wi-Fi, Bluetooth or near field communication (NFC).**

* Wikipedia – Mobile device, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mobile_device